

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION ON PERFORMANCE OF COMPOSITE JOINTS WITH EMBEDDED STEEL PLATE

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ABSTRACT

Joint design is one of the crucial tasks in airframe structure design, especially for joining metal structures with composite structures. As composite material gaining its popularity in aviation, many new kinds of joints are being proposed. Therefore, a comprehensive understanding of their mechanical properties, such as the strength and failure mechanism, has great importance for the improvement of structural reliability and joint efficiency.

In this study, a new kind of adhesively bonded metal-composite joint was designed to investigate the potential improvement in joint strength and stress distribution. One end of the steel plate, which was a large rectangular region, was embed in composite laminate. The other end was much narrow and extended from the inside of the composite laminate. During the specimen manufacturing procedure, a steel plate was machined into a particular shape and a corresponding carbon fiber preform, with the carbon fiber tows held by polyester threads in a certain ply sequence, was constructed. The steel plate was inserted into the cavity of the preform. Combination of the steel plate and carbon fiber preform was then put into a matched mould and was co-cured by injecting liquid BMI resin. Static tensile tests were then conducted on two kinds of metal-composite joints with varied shapes of steel plate' tip, which were tapered and blunt respectively. Test results showed the one with blunt tip had higher final failure strength, reason of which maybe the tapered tip led to unsymmetry in stress distribution across the section. It indicated that the unsymmetry load distribution between the two sides resulted in earlier damage in the interface between steel plates and composite laminates, and easier fracture around the edge of the composite laminates where the steel plates extended from. In the end, comparisons between this new metal-composite joint with tradition adhesively bonded references show the improvement in joint strength and joint efficiency.

Keywords: adhesively bonded, embedded steel plate, failure mechanism, joint strength, metal-composite joint

1 INTRODUCTION

An origin type of metallic insert composite structure was proposed by Camanho^[1], which was designed to improve the behavior of bolted joints in composite laminate by inserting a thin sleeve into the hole. The metallic inserts were adhesively bonded to the composite laminates. Therefore, the stress concentration around the hole can be reduced and an increase in strength can be obtained. A similar metallic inserts composite laminate structures was introduced by Dvorak^[2], whose research showed that adhesively bonded tongue and groove joints between steel and composite laminates have higher

tensile strength than conventional strap joints. Melograna et al.^[3] inserted a steel plate with perforation into glass fiber fabrics to diminish the difficulty in joining the fiber reinforced composites and steel caused by elastic mismatch. And it turned out that the perforation in the steel led to stronger adhesive joints, for which the reasons maybe two mechanism: reduced elastic mismatch between the two adherends and mechanical interlocking. Furthermore, they investigated the tensile properties of nine geometrically different tongue-and-groove joints of steel plates and composite laminates^[4]. With the increase number of the tongues, the strength of the tongue-and-groove joints grew obviously and exceeded that of single lap joints. If the tip of the tongue changed to a lollipop shape, the strength can be enhanced because the circular region of the tongue could mechanically hold on after an initial load drop. Matous et al.^[5] established finite element model to evaluate local stresses in the adhesion and adherends of the tongue-and-groove joints. He pointed out that the application of tongue-and-groove joints have significant advantages in joining thick laminates over single and double lap joints. Canyurt et al.^[6] developed non-linear prediction models using genetic algorithm(GA), which were validated with experimental data. The results indicated that the joint strength can be increased by properly selecting design parameters, such as tongue length, bondline thickness, the pre-stress near the free edges of bondline, the material of the joining parts, etc. Ucsnik et al.^[7] experimentally investigated the static tensile strength of hybrid metal-composite joint, which embeds the metal structure into the reinforce fibres without drilling holes or destroying the reinforcing fibre bundles. Tensile test results demonstrated remarkable increase in the ultimate tensile load and mean local strains at maximum force. This new kind of integrative joining technology has high potential in providing better load-transfer and damage tolerance.

The present work differs from what the references showed above, which is about almost totally inserting a whole steel plate into a composite laminate and a narrow part of the steel plate extends from the inside, as shown in Fig.1. This is part of the practical empennage structure. The composite laminates are the aerodynamic surfaces and the steel inserts are used the joint the rudder and the stabilizing plane. During the manufacturing process of this structure, the steel plate and the composite laminates were co-cured in a certain mould and the steel plate was adhesively bonded to the composite laminates by the resin layer. There were few research work about this kind of structures so far and the previous studies were all about tongue-and-groove (T&G) joints between metal plate and composite laminates. As shown in Fig.2, the metal tongue is adhesively bonded to the composite laminate groove. There is a common place between these two kinds of structures, that is the composite laminates in these two structures are subjected to in-plane loading. While the distinction between them contains two parts, one is that the present one inserts a larger area of metal plate (tongue) into composite laminates (groove). This can help the increasing the load capacity by the compression between the metallic inserts and composite laminates. The other difference is that the metallic inserts in present one are adhesively bonded to the composite laminates on all sides, while the tradition T&G joint only two lateral sides are bonded together. So the present study mainly focused on this new kind of composite joints with embedded steel plate, investigating the load capacity and analyzing the failure behavior when subjected to tensile load.

Figure 1: The composite joint with embedded steel plate

Figure 2: Tongue-and groove (T&G) joint structure

2 MATERIALS AND SPECIMEN MANUFACTURE PROCEDURE

The composite laminates were made from T700 warp knitted fabric and resin #6808, while the metallic inserts are 45# steel. The composite laminate consists of 72 layers for and the ply sequences are designed as $[-45/0/45/90]_{9S}$, and the steel plates are cut into a certain shape and size. The manufacturing process was selected as Resin Transfer Molding, RTM and a corresponding mould was designed and machined in advance.

Once the preparations above were fully finished, the carbon fiber T700 fabrics were made into a carbon fiber preform as designed. And then, the steel plate was inserted into the preform to construct the new hybrid composite-metal joint. After this, the joint was put into the mould as a whole and a compression load was applied to eliminate the gap, porosity and air inside. Then liquid BMI resin #6808 was injected into the mould through a bump until the resin infiltrate all the carbon fiber. In the end, the whole mould was put into an oven and the temperature was set to keep 2 or more hours at 200°C. After the resin was completely cured and the whole mould naturally cool to room temperature, the structure was taken out from the mould and some modification work should be done, such as deburring, grinding and cleaning. The final specimens were shown in Fig.3 as below. And ultrasonic flaw detector was used to inspect the quality of the specimens. The ultrasonic C-scan images for Group A specimens were reported in Fig.4. It can be easily found that most of the composite laminates have good quality, but the quality of the bonding area of the steel plates and the composite laminates can hardly be detected.

Figure 3: The actual specimens used in this study

Figure 4: Ultrasonic C-scan images for Group A specimens

3 EXPERIMENTAL TEST PROCEDURE

Two configurations of the specimen were chosen to conduct tensile tests, one is the composite joint with embedded blunt-tip steel plate as shown in Fig. 5, the other is the composite joint with embedded tapered-tip steel plate as shown in Fig. 6. For identifying the damage process of the structure during tensile tests, strain gauges were used to monitor the axial strain values at below locations on the specimen surface as shown in Fig. 7. Tensile tests were performed on the Instron servo-hydraulic machine 8803 with a load capacity of 500 kN. Tests were carried out at room temperature and at a fixed loading rate of 0.5mm/min. The gripping pressure was set about 35 MPa, which is sufficient to prevent slipping of the specimen but insufficient to cause end crushing. The experimental set-up was shown in Fig. 8.

Figure 5: Configuration of composite joint with embedded blunt-tip steel plate

Figure 6: Configuration of composite joint with embedded tapered-tip steel plate

Figure 7: Locations of strain gauges during the tensile test

Figure 8: Experimental set-up for the tensile test

4 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The tests were divided into two groups, labeled as group A and B, representing composite joints with blunt-tip steel plate and tapered-tip steel plate respectively. Group A had three specimens and Group B had two specimens, geometry dimension of which were all listed below in the Table 1.

Group	A			B	
No.	A1	A2	A3	B1	B2
Thickness(mm)	9.12	9.16	8.93	9.06	8.90
	9.11	9.24	8.90	9.06	8.92
	9.05	9.21	8.92	9.02	8.96
	8.99	9.48	9.03	8.90	8.93
	9.03	9.19	9.08	8.90	8.92
	9.04	9.19	9.04	8.95	8.84
Width(mm)	101.09	100.06	100.97	100.97	100.06
	101.00	100.03	101.07	100.94	100.07
	101.01	100.05	100.97	100.97	100.07

Table 1: Geometry dimensions of the specimens

The tensile load and displacement were recorded through the computer automatically, and the load-displacement curves were summarized in Fig. 9. As can be seen, Group A had larger load capacity than Group B. The average ultimate failure load of the composite joint with blunt-tip steel inserts was 41.2kN and there existed a large dispersion as high as 14.2%. This may be caused by the manufacture procedure and the adhesion bonding is very difficult to control and inspect. As ultra C-scan images roughly showed the property of the laminates, but could not demonstrate the poor bonding inside the specimens. The initial slopes of the curves were almost the same, but when the tensile load increased to 25kN, the curves began to separate from each other. And before the final failure happened, there were several cracking sounds. When the load sharply decreased, obvious cracks emerged near the root of the steel plate, as shown in Fig. 10. As for Group B, the ultimate failure load tended to be much smaller than Group A. As shown in Fig. 11, the average failure load of Group B was almost 37.5% lower than Group A. While the ultimate failure displacement of Group B was also much smaller than Group A, which indicated that the two Group had the same structural stiffness but had large differences in strength. This might because the unsymmetry of the tapered-tip steel plate, which could induced earlier damage along the bonding area.

Figure 9: Tensile load-displacement curves for Group A and Group B

Specimen No.	A1	A2	A3	B1	B2
Ultimate load(kN)	46.5	42.2	34.9	27.8	23.7
Failure displacement(mm)	0.84	0.73	0.52	0.32	0.26

Table 2: Summary of the tensile test results

Figure 10 Cracks generated when the final failure happened

Figure 11: Comparison of the failure load of group A and B

Two microscopy specimens were extracted from two specimens of the two groups respectively. As shown in Fig. 12, the blunt-tip and tapered-tip were inspected by magnifying 63 and 125 times using a microscope. For Group A, the top and bottom surface of the steel plate were directly attached to the composite plies, while the adhesive layer hardly could be seen. Around the blunt-tip, there was an adhesive layer, but its thickness was not uniform. For Group B, the delta area between the tapered-tip and composite plies was filled with resin.

Figure 12: Microscopic images of the blunt-tip and the tapered-tip of the insert steel plate

The relations between strain values corresponding to the points demonstrated in Fig. 7 and the tensile loads were shown in Fig. 13. For Group A, points 1-5 and 1-6 had the largest strain; and points 1-2 and 1-3 came second; while points 1-1 and 1-4 had the smallest strain. It indicated that the load transferred to the middle of composite laminates was larger than to the two sides. As the strain value at point 1-5, when the final failure happened, was only approximately $1200\mu\epsilon$, which is far below the failure strain of composite laminates. Group B showed similar results, but the strain values were much smaller because the failure load tended to be lower. Although the damage of the adhesive and the interface cannot be observed, it can be empirically speculated that the initial damage was very likely due to the debonding around the tip corner of the steel plates.

Figure 13: Strain-load curves of the two group specimens

5 CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

This composite joint with embedded steel plate can be applied in the connector structure between aerodynamic surfaces and the airfoil surfaces of missiles or unmanned aerial vehicles. They can be adhesively joint or hybrid joint. It is hard to detect the damages of the structure because the adhesive film between the metallic inserts and the composite laminates is inside the structure and the quality of the adhesive-metal interface can hardly be inspected. This article focuses on the tensile strength and stiffness of the metallic inserts composite structure. And two forms of inserts structure were compared: the blunt-tip steel plate inserts and the tapered-tip steel plate inserts. The following conclusions can be drawn:

1. The tensile strength of composite joint with embedded blunt-tip steel plate larger than that of composite joint with embedded tapered-tip steel plate.
2. The structural stiffness of these two kinds of structure are similar, which indicated the shape of the steel plate's tip only influences the structural strength. It is analyzed that the unsymmetry of the tapered-tip introduces serious stress concentration around the tip, leading to earlier damage of the bonding area.
3. When the final fracture happened and the load dropped sharply, it was observed that obvious cracks appeared in the composite laminates around the root of the outside-extended steel plates and the steel plates were all right.
4. The stain data showed that the load transferred through the shear between steel plates and composite laminates was very limited, which was far away from causing the damage of the laminates. And the failure mechanism was the adhesively debonding around the tip corner of the steel plates.

This paper only carried out the experimental study on structural strength of the composite joint with embedded steel plate and compared two different shapes of the steel plate. In the future, a finite element model should be established to predict the structural strength and to analyze the failure mechanism and damage propagation. So it would be useful to optimize some influencing factors, such as geometry parameters and properties of the adhesive, and help improving the design of this structure eventually.

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